

Republic of the Philippines

HOUSE OF REPRESENTATIVES

Quezon City, Metro Manila

SENATE

Pasay City, Metro Manila

TWENTIETH CONGRESS

First Regular Session

HOUSE BILL NO. _____

SENATE BILL NO. _____

Legislative Proposal by Jonelle Peter C. Muñoz (*Citizen of the Republic*)

AN ACT

SETTING MINIMUM GOOD GOVERNANCE MEMBERSHIP REQUIREMENTS FOR LOCAL CHIEF EXECUTIVES SUCH AS MAYOR AND GOVERNOR

1 **SECTION 1. Short Title**

2 This Act shall be known as the “**Good Governance Membership Requirements Act**
3 **for Local Chief Executives**”.

4

5 **SECTION 2. Declaration of Policy**

6 It is hereby declared the policy of the State to promote transparency, accountability, and
7 good governance among all public officials, particularly Local Chief Executives. This Act
8 establishes minimum good governance standards that every Mayor and Governor shall
9 uphold and implement during their term of office, as a demonstration of integrity, public
10 trust, and commitment to genuine service to the Filipino people.

11

12 **SECTION 3. Freedom of Information and Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinances**

13 The Local Chief Executive must have passed and implemented:

14 • *Freedom of Information (FOI) Ordinance*, comparable in quality to that of Pasig
15 City, including a penalty clause for non-compliance; and

16 • *Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance*, to prevent the concentration of political power
17 within families and promote equal opportunity in public service.

1 **SECTION 4. Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth (SALN)**

2 The Local Chief Executive must have a Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth
3 (SALN) publicly available from the first year of public service up to the present, if
4 incumbent. Such SALNs must be accessible in accordance with existing laws and
5 regulations. Sensitive information protected under the Data Privacy Act may be
6 redacted, provided that transparency and accountability are not compromised.

7

8 **SECTION 5. Bank Secrecy Waiver**

9 The Local Chief Executive must have executed a bank secrecy waiver authorizing the
10 Office of the Ombudsman to access their bank records for official investigation
11 purposes. The waiver may be made public at the discretion of the official.

12

13 **SECTION 6. Wealth Donation Affidavit**

14 The Local Chief Executive must have publicized a notarized affidavit of declaration
15 stating that all wealth in excess of Five Million Pesos (₱5,000,000.00) shall be donated
16 to the education sector, especially for building schools and providing scholarships to
17 Filipino children.

18 The Local Chief Executive must have publicized a notarized authorization letter
19 addressed to all officials of the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) and the Register of
20 Deeds, authorizing them to transfer all real estate properties in excess of one thousand
21 (1,000) square meters to the education sector for the purpose of building schools. All
22 transfer fees and taxes shall be waived.

23 The Local Chief Executive must have publicized a notarized affidavit of declaration
24 stating that all unexplained real estate properties *abroad* shall be transferred back to the
25 Republic of the Philippines.

26 All donations made pursuant to this Act shall be exempt from all applicable national and
27 local taxes. The Department of Finance and the Bureau of Internal Revenue shall issue
28 the necessary rules and regulations to implement this Section.

29

30 **SECTION 7. Education and Development Requirements**

31 a. *No School Backlog.* The Local Chief Executives must have no school backlog at
32 any level from Kindergarten to Grade 12 and up to college, as certified by the
33 Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education
34 (CHED).

35 b. *Adequate Schools for OSYA.* After ensuring compliance with Section 6a, the city,
36 municipality, or province under the Local Chief Executive must have adequate

1 schools and learning facilities proportionate to the number of Out-of-School Youth
2 and Adults (OSYA) within its jurisdiction.

- 3 c. *Free College Tuition and Stipend.* The Local Chief Executives must ensure free
4 college tuition fees and provide a stipend allowance of Five Thousand Pesos
5 (₱5,000) per semester to students whose families have a household income of
6 less than Ten Thousand Pesos (₱10,000) per month.

7
8 **SECTION 8. Health and Medical Services Requirements**

- 9 a. *No Hospital Bed Backlog.* The Local Chief Executives must have no hospital bed
10 backlog in public hospitals within their jurisdiction, as certified by the Department
11 of Health (DOH).
- 12 b. *Adequate Medical Specialists.* The Local Chief Executive must have adequate
13 number of medical specialists, including but not limited to heart specialists, brain
14 specialists, and other critical care professionals, to address the health needs of
15 their constituents. Emergency patients shall not wait more than four (4) hours for
16 life-saving procedures or surgeries.
- 17 c. *Free Hospital Care for Low-Income Families.* The Local Chief Executives must
18 ensure free hospital medicines, surgeries, and other medical services for families
19 with a household income of less than Ten Thousand Pesos (₱10,000) per month.
20 For other patients who have been employed for at least twelve (12) months and
21 whose salary exceeds Ten Thousand Pesos (₱10,000) per month, the maximum
22 hospital bill shall not exceed one month's salary of the highest income-earning
23 member of the family.

24
25 **SECTION 9. Financial Accountability and Audit Compliance**

26 The local government under a Local Chief Executive must maintain the highest
27 standards of financial management and accountability. To ensure compliance:

- 28 a. *Internal Controls and Reporting.* The Local Chief Executive must have
29 established and maintained proper internal controls over all financial
30 transactions, have ensured timely submission of financial reports, and have
31 monitored subordinate offices to prevent irregularities and mismanagement.
- 32 b. *Audit Compliance Incentives.* The local government is encouraged to maintain
33 exemplary financial performance, as reflected in the annual Commission on Audit
34 (COA) examination. The local government under the Local Chief Executive must
35 have no Notices of Disallowances (NOD), Notices of Charge (NOC), or Notices
36 of Suspension (NOS).
- 37 c. *Exemption for Indirect Findings.* Audit observations or findings that result from
38 actions, delays, or omissions of subordinate personnel or external agencies shall
39 not be counted against the Local Chief Executive's compliance with this Section.

1 Only audit findings directly attributable to the Local Chief Executive’s decisions or
2 negligence shall be considered.

3

4 **SECTION 10. Transparency and Accountability Measures**

5 *Public Ledger of Contracts and Documents.* The Local Chief Executive must maintain a
6 public ledger of all contracts, agreements, and official documents signed or executed in
7 the performance of their duties and responsibilities.

8 *Transparent Local Website.* The Local Chief Executive must maintain a transparent,
9 regularly updated, and publicly accessible local government website, modeled after best
10 practices such as those implemented in Singapore (www.gov.sg) and Sweden
11 (sweden.se).

12 The website shall contain, at a minimum, the following documents since the effectivity of
13 the Local Government Code of 1991, with priority given to those issued within the six (6)
14 years immediately preceding the passage of this Act, where applicable.

- 15 • All local ordinances and resolutions;
- 16 • All local government contracts, including Memoranda of Agreement (MOA) and
17 Memoranda of Understanding (MOU);
- 18 • A public ledger of all contracts and official documents signed by the Local Chief
19 Executive;
- 20 • A transcript of all regular and special sessions;
- 21 • Financial documents, including annual financial statements, budget utilization
22 reports, and final Commission on Audit (COA) audit reports; and
- 23 • All other public documents required by law to be posted or disclosed to the
24 public.

25

26 **SECTION 11. Designated Spokesperson Requirement**

27 The Local Chief Executive must have one designated spokesperson, ideally a lawyer or
28 reputable journalist with at least three (3) years of professional experience, to explain all
29 public documents signed. An individual with a background in contract law is preferred.

30 The designated spokesperson shall work full-time, eight (8) hours per day, five (5) days
31 per week, similar to an ordinary government employee, to provide explanations of all
32 public documents signed by the Local Chief Executive.

33

34 **SECTION 12. Full-Time Service Ordinance**

35 The Local Chief Executive and other elective officials *must have rendered full-time*
36 *service from 8:00 a.m. to 5:00 p.m., five days a week*, similar to ordinary government

1 employees. They must have enacted an ordinance implementing and enforcing this
2 requirement.

3 The Local Chief Executives and other elective officials must have publicized a daily
4 accomplishment report of at least five hundred (500) words, summarizing tasks and
5 outcomes completed during the day.

6

7 **SECTION 13. Monthly Public Forum**

8 The Local Chief Executive must conduct at least one *public forum* per month, lasting not
9 less than *two (2) hours*, to engage constituents, promote transparency, and gather
10 feedback on governance and public service initiatives.

11 The public forum must be open to everyone and must include representatives from
12 diverse sectors, including at least one teacher, one student, one member of a civil
13 society organization, one engineer, one architect, one lawyer, one accountant, one IT
14 professional, one unemployed person, one philosopher, one businessperson, and one
15 public policymaker.

16 The time and venue of the forum must be made public at least one week before the
17 scheduled forum.

18

19 **SECTION 14. Notarized Transcript of Official Meetings**

20 All meetings related to the duties and responsibilities of the Local Chief Executive must
21 have *notarized transcripts or certified minutes*, which must be made *accessible on the*
22 *local government website*, ensuring that decisions are made in the best interest of the
23 people and the greater good.

24

25 **SECTION 15. Formation of Strong Political Party**

26 The first Local Chief Executive who successfully complies with all mandatory good
27 governance requirements set forth in this Act is encouraged to form a strong political
28 party within sixty (60) days.

29 If the first compliant Local Chief Executive chooses not to form the political party, the
30 second or any succeeding compliant Local Chief Executive may do so. All Local Chief
31 Executives who comply with all good governance requirements for three consecutive
32 years shall have automatic and irrevocable membership in the new political party.

33 The new political party shall establish minimum membership requirements for non-LCE
34 and non-public official members, consistent with the principles of good governance and
35 ethical public service as provided in this Act.

36

1 **SECTION 16. Voluntary Membership and Recognition**

2 Membership under the good governance requirements established in this Act shall be
3 entirely voluntary. Recognition shall serve as:

- 4 1. A public affirmation of competence, transparency and moral excellence; and
- 5 2. A qualification to pioneer the formation of a strong political party that aspires to
6 reshape the future of the nation and, in its ideal form, contribute to a legacy that
7 may forever change the course of humankind.

8 Non-membership shall not result in any penalty or administrative consequence.

9

10 **SECTION 17. Separability Clause**

11 If any provision of this Act is held invalid or unconstitutional, no other provision shall be
12 affected thereby.

13

14 **SECTION 18. Repealing Clause**

15 All laws, presidential decrees, executive orders, rules, regulations, local ordinances, or
16 parts thereof that are inconsistent with any provision of this Act are hereby repealed,
17 amended, or modified accordingly. In case of conflict between this Act and any existing
18 issuance, the provisions of this Act shall prevail.

19

20 **SECTION 19. Effectivity**

21 This Act shall take effect upon its approval.

22

23 Approved: _____

24

25

26 Date Core Idea First Published (Version 1.0): October 18, 2025

27 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17394303>

28

29 Legislative Proposal (Version 1.1), Proposed Law #117: November 13 to 17, 2025

30 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17598576>

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32 Legislative Proposal (Version 1.2), Proposed Law #117: November 13 to 19, 2025

33 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17644898>

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1 **ANNEX A**

2 *Alternative Mandatory Version in the future*

3 The author initially considered having a penalty clause. However, he understands that in
4 the current state of local governance, it will be difficult to comply with majority of the
5 sections of this Act.

6 The penalty provisions below can be initiated by the future Congress, when competence
7 and transparency become the norm in government, and when at least one hundred
8 (100) Local Chief Executives have successfully complied with all the good governance
9 requirements set forth in this Act.

10 **AN ACT**

11 **ESTABLISHING MANDATORY GOOD GOVERNANCE STANDARDS**
12 **FOR LOCAL CHIEF EXECUTIVES SUCH AS MAYOR AND GOVERNOR**

13 **SECTION 17. Administrative Penalties for Non-Compliance**

14 The Local Chief Executive who fails to comply with the provisions of this Act shall be
15 subject to the following administrative penalties, without prejudice to other penalties
16 under existing laws:

- 17 1. *First offense:* Written warning and public notice of non-compliance from the
18 Department of Interior and Local Government, itemizing all provisions of this Act
19 that have not been complied with;
- 20 2. *Second offense:* Fine equivalent to one month’s salary, to be remitted to the
21 DepEd or CHED for providing scholarships to qualified students;
- 22 3. *Third offense:* Fine equivalent to one year’s salary, to be remitted to the DepEd
23 or CHED for providing scholarships to qualified students;
- 24 4. *Fourth offense:* Suspension from office for thirty (30) days. The Local Chief
25 Executive shall be required to publicize a written explanation letter detailing the
26 reasons for non-compliance and a plan to implement the provisions within the
27 next twelve (12) months;
- 28 5. *Fifth offense:* Suspension from office for six (6) months and referral to the
29 Ombudsman for possible administrative sanctions due to neglect of duties and
30 responsibilities;
- 31 6. *Six offense:* Perpetual revocation of Good Governance Membership. The Local
32 Chief Executive shall no longer be recognized as compliant under this Act and
33 shall be ineligible for recognition associated with membership.

34 During the suspension, the Local Chief Executive shall be temporarily replaced by the
35 Vice Mayor or Vice Governor, as applicable.

ANNEX B

Name of Mayor / Governor: _____ City/Province: _____

GOOD GOVERNANCE CHECKLIST REQUIREMENT FOR MAYOR AND GOVERNOR			
#	Requirement	Specific Requirement	Status ✓ or x
1	Freedom of Information Ordinance and Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance	FOI Ordinance passed (with penalty clause)	
		Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance passed	
2	SALN Transparency	All SALN publicized from first year of being a public official up to present (if incumbent)	
3	Bank Secrecy Waiver	Executed bank secrecy waiver allowing Ombudsman access (must include both bank accounts in the Philippines and abroad)	
4	Wealth Donation Affidavit	Publicized a notarized affidavit stating that all wealth in excess of 5M or 10M shall be donated to education sector, specifically for building schools and providing scholarships to Filipino children	
		Publicized a notarized affidavit authorizing all public officials of Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) and Registry of Deeds (RD) to transfer all Real Estate Properties in excess of 1,000 sqm	

4	Wealth Donation Affidavit	Publicized a notarized affidavit authorizing all public officials of the government to transfer all unexplained real estate properties abroad to the Republic of the Philippines	
5	Education Sector Requirements	Certification of No School Backlog from DepEd and CHED	
		Adequate schools for Out-of-School-Youth (OSYA)	
		Free college tuition fee for low-income families and P5,000 per semester stipend for eligible students	
6	Health Sector Requirements	Certification of No Hospital Bed Backlog from DOH	
		Adequate doctors, surgeons and specialists for life saving health conditions	
		Free hospital bills and medicines for families earning less than P10,000 per month	
7	Financial Accountability	Proper internal controls and timely reports	
		No COA findings such as Notice of Disallowance (NOD), Notice of Charge (NOC) and Notice of Suspension (NOS) (Audit observations or findings that result from actions, delays, or omissions of subordinate personnel or external agencies are excluded)	

8	Transparency Measures	Public ledger of all contracts and documents signed	
		Fully transparency website similar to the website of Singapore and Denmark with all public documents	
9	Designated Spokesperson	Has spokesperson (lawyer/journalist, 3+ yrs experience) to explain all public documents signed (priority are those contracts worth more than P500,000)	
10	Full-Time Service	Works 8am to 5pm, 5 days per week (must have enacted an ordinance to institutionalize this along with other elected and high ranking officials)	
11	Monthly Public Forum	Regularly conducts public forum (At least two hours per month. Ideal two hours per week. Includes required representatives.)	
12	Meeting Transparency	Notarized transcript of all official meetings (Signature in just the first and acknowledgement page to save time, while thumbmark in all pages.)	

<p style="text-align: center;">13</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Political Party Formation (Optional)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Eligible after full compliance of all good governance minimum requirements</p>	
<p style="text-align: right;">Total (as of November 2025)</p>			<p style="text-align: center;">13/12</p>

ANNEX C

All pages of Annex C will be published online

RECEIVED BY	REMARKS / NOTE / PROPOSED AMENDMENT
	Approved: First Yes
	Approved: 2 nd Yes
	Disapproved: First No
	Approved: 3 rd Yes
	Approved: 4 th Yes

ANNEX C

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ANNEX C

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ANNEX C

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Written for Filipino children deprived of education and a better future
because of corruption and greed.